

Privacy and data confidentiality for Official Statistics: new challenges and new tools

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1 INTRODUCTION

The modern society is undergoing a process of massive *datafication* [1]. The availability of new digital data sources represents an opportunity for Statistical Offices (SO) to complement traditional statistics as well as to produce novel statistical products with improved timeliness and relevance. However, such opportunities come with important challenges in almost every aspect – methodological, business models, data governance, regulation, organizational and others. The new scenario calls for an evolution of the *modus operandi* adopted by SO also with respect to privacy and data confidentiality, that is the focus of the present contribution. We propose here a discussion framework focused on the prospective combination of advanced Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) methods with Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMC) techniques.

2 CHANGING SCENARIO: FROM MONOPOLY TO ECOSYSTEM

For decades, the data business has been a natural monopoly centered around SO: no other entity had the technical and legal capability to collect and process large-scale data. In the traditional operation model, illustrated in Fig. 1(a), SO ingest internally all source (micro-)data, either directly from the data subjects via surveys and censuses or indirectly through administrative registers. The input source data collected in the back-end are then processed centrally to deliver two types of front-end data in output: (i) official statistics for the general public; and (ii) more detailed data for further processing by expert users and researchers downstream the data flow.

The legal mandate of SO includes two important obligations that can be summarized as ‘*closed input and open output*’. On the input side (back-end), SO must preserve the confidentiality of the (micro-)data in order to protect the privacy of data subjects. On the output side (front-end), SO are committed to publish openly the processed output data, so as to ensure that all potential users get the same information and do so at the same time. The motivations and implications of both obligations are intimately connected to the democratic role of Official Statistics. However, in terms of real-world application, there is an unavoidable conflict between these two goals, since by definition the output data carry non-zero information about the input data (otherwise they would be useless), i.e., they always reveal ‘something’ about the input. On the front-end, SO must determine whether what can be inferred from the output about the input can be tolerated or not, i.e., whether it remains uninfluential for the privacy of the individual data subjects or instead put it at risk. Such determination must be done case-by-case and this is the goal of the so-called Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) function (ref. Fig. 1(a)). When critical cases are detected, SDC methods seek to strike a reasonable compromise between the two conflicting goals of preserving accuracy and completeness of the output and at the same time confidentiality of the input. In practice, this involves limiting and/or degrading the output data *in a controlled manner*, typically by suppression of selected elements, injection of controlled noise, restrictions on the type and/or number of iterated queries performed on the

Figure 1: The change of scenario surrounding Official Statistics

same input dataset, or a combination of the above. In other words, a trade-off is in place between accuracy and completeness of the output (hence its utility) and confidentiality of the input [2, 3].

The new scenario illustrated in Fig. 1(b) yields several elements of novelty. Instead of dominating the ‘data monopoly’ as in the past, SO are now one species of a larger ‘data ecosystem’ where different organizations, including public institutions and private companies, engage in the collection and processing of (new) different kinds of data about citizens, companies, goods etc. For SO this change has implications on both sides. In the back-end, there are new potential data sources to be accessed, in addition to traditional survey/census and administrative data, but the peculiarities of such new sources might require alternative access models other than direct ingestion of raw input data [4]. On the front-end, the expert users downstream the processing flow have now increased possibilities to combine the data obtained by SO with other external data sources, an aspect that exacerbates the challenge for SDC.

3 INPUT PRIVACY VS OUTPUT PRIVACY

Hereafter we provide an abstract view about the relations between input data and output data and then introduce the notions of ‘input privacy’ and ‘output privacy’ that are sometimes used in the literature (see e.g. [5]). Finally, we discuss how these categories map to the new SO scenario described in the previous section.

Let x_1 and x_2 denote two generic input data set consisting of confidential (personal) records and $y = f(x_1, x_2)$ the desired output information we wish to extract. The latter can take an arbitrary form, including e.g. a summary indicator, a set of regression coefficients or a frequency table. What is relevant for our discussion is the multi-party

Figure 2: Computation vs. Inference.

scenario where the elements x_1, x_2 and y belong to different organizations (parties), and the input data cannot be revealed to any other party. We call ‘computation’ the task of extracting the desired output data y from the input data x_1, x_2 and denote by $f(\cdot)$ the computing function. We call ‘inference’ the task of extracting some (partial) information about one of the input components, say x_1 , based on knowledge of the output y and possibly other external data (including the other input x_2). Let $g(\cdot)$ denote the best possible inference function and \hat{x}_1 what can be inferred about the input. As represented in Fig. 2, the computation and inference tasks go in opposite directions. In this scenario we distinguish two separate but complementary problems:

- **Input privacy problem:** *How to enable the output party obtain the desired output y without requiring the input parties to reveal their respective inputs x_1 and x_2 ?* If the output can be derived from a single input source (single input party) and is not confidential, the simplest option is to let the input party execute the computation and then pass the result to the output party. If instead the desired output requires the fusion of input data from different parties, a possible solution is offered by Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMC) techniques. In a nutshell, With SMC methods the input data are transformed into so-called ‘secret shares’ and passed to a set of (three or more) intermediate ‘computing parties’ that collectively form the SMC infrastructure. The secret shares are produced in a way that, *under certain conditions* (attack model), do not reveal anything about the input source data (non-invertibility) but still allow to compute exactly the correct output (homomorphism). A general introduction to SMC and secret sharing can be found in [6], while examples of practical applications are found in [7, 8].
- **Output privacy problem:** *Given that y can be computed in some way, how to ensure that what can be inferred back about the input, i.e., \hat{x}_1 , remains below a certain tolerable level?* This problem is addressed by SDC methods.

Since SDC and SMC are targeting different but complementary problems, it is natural to consider their combination. From the above definitions it should be clear that, in principle, both ‘input privacy’ and ‘output privacy’ problems may be encountered at both sides. In other words, in the new scenario we may consider adopting some combination of SMC and SDC in the back-end as well as on the front-end.

As to the back-end, SMC may play an important role when joint processing of multiple data sources from different parties is required but direct ingestion of raw input data by SO is not possible, e.g., due to legal restrictions or business considerations (as in [7]). This includes cases where the source data are held by the private business sector. Considering the special trust endowment of SO, who plays the role of output party in the back-end, it is reasonable to assume that non-disclosure agreements and legal provisions are sufficient to solve the ‘output privacy’ problem in the back-end, waiving the need to introduce SDC tools on this side.

Conversely, SDC solutions will remain crucial on the front-end. SMC can be used on the front-end to enable joint processing of confidential input data from SO and other data holders (ref. rightmost part of Fig. 1(b)). More in general, a wise combination of SMC and SDC might help to achieve a higher level of overall confidentiality in the new wilder scenario, where increased availability of external data sources amplifies the non-disclosure challenges. Some initial work in this direction is starting to appear in the field of Official Statistics [9], while commercial implementation of SMC already include some simple safeguards for disclosure control [8].

4 CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

The new ‘datafied’ scenario requires SO to widen their traditional approach to privacy and data confidentiality. Purely regulatory means in the back-end and simple SDC methods in the front-end might not suffice any more. Embracing novel tools such as SMC, in combination with more advanced forms of SDC, seems to be a promising direction. More in general, SO need to develop a more systematic and articulated approach towards ‘privacy engineering’ to face the new challenges posed by an increasingly complex data ecosystem.

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